

Development of a Bioimpedance Probe for Enhanced Tissue Identification in the Upper Aerodigestive Tract

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Abstract—Upper Aerodigestive Tract (UADT) cancers are prevalent and often fatal due to late diagnosis. Like many other biological tissues, UADT tissue consists of multiple layers, with cancer commonly developing in the epithelial layer, before spreading to deeper structures. Accurate identification of each layer can aid in early diagnosis, resulting in improved treatment outcomes. This study presents a bioimpedance sensing probe with optimized electrode placement for diagnosis of UADT cancers. The probe, designed to fit a laryngoscope’s working channel, is equipped with four electrodes, allowing for a total of 12 impedance measurements. To determine the electrode position on the probe, a novel optimization method is used to enhance the difference between sensitivity distributions for different measurements. Experiments performed using simulations validate the probe’s effectiveness in retrieving more information to be used for tissue identification, demonstrating its potential for real-time, on-site cancer detection.

I. INTRODUCTION

Upper Aerodigestive Tract (UADT) cancers, including malignancies of the oral cavity, pharynx, larynx, and esophagus, are both common and highly fatal, largely due to late diagnosis. For Oral Squamous Cell Carcinoma (OSCC), more than half of patients are diagnosed at an advanced stage, resulting in a 5-year survival rate of less than 50% [1]. Diagnosis typically involves visual inspection followed by a biopsy of suspicious areas. However, early-stage misdiagnosis is frequent, as the cancer often resembles other benign conditions, leading to delayed treatment [2]. Early-stage oral cancers generally develop in the top layer of the tissue, which is the epithelium layer. As the cancer progresses, it spreads to deeper structures including the lamina propria and submucosa layers [3].

Previous studies suggest electrical bioimpedance spectroscopy (BIS) as an accurate, cost-effective, and non-invasive method for real-time, on-site, and preoperative diagnosis of UADT cancer [4]. Impedance, which is the measure of opposition to alternating current, comprises both resistance and reactance. It is typically expressed as a complex value, with the real part representing resistance and the imaginary part representing reactance. Several factors influence impedance, including the electrical properties of the measured material: electrical conductivity (σ) and relative permittivity (ϵ_r). Since cancer alters the cellular structure

of tissue, these electrical properties change accordingly, enabling BIS to detect cancerous tissue [5].

A study by Cheng and Savarimuthu examines the advantages and limitations of four BIS configurations. It emphasizes the benefits of the tripolar and tetrapolar configurations, including their wider sensitivity distribution, which allows for the measurement of deeper regions, as well as their ability to reduce the impact of electrode surface area and contact impedance in measurements, ultimately increasing measurement accuracy. For the tripolar configuration, excitation current is injected to the tissue via one electrode and to the ground electrode, while two other electrodes are used for voltage measurement [6].

Many studies utilize probes with symmetrically arranged electrodes, resulting in equal distances between the electrodes. Notably, the spatial sensitivity distribution is linked to the inter-electrode distances, with greater distances enhancing sensitivity in deeper regions [7]. Consequently, symmetrical electrode arrangements yield identical impedance measurements in homogeneous materials, which is not optimal for analyzing layered materials such as the UADT. In contrast, a non-symmetric electrode arrangement with varying inter-electrode distances enables multiple effective measurement depths. Optimizing the position of electrodes to achieve a wide range of sensitivity distributions, enabling certain configurations to primarily capture information from the tissue surface, while other configurations capture information about deeper structures. This highlights the need for a new electrode position optimization method, to achieve a more effective measurement of different UADT tissue layers and analyze their health status.

This paper presents a BIS sensing probe with optimized electrode placement, which is designed to pass through a laryngoscope’s working channel, contact suspicious tissue in the UADT, and aid in cancer diagnosis.

II. METHODS

As shown in Fig. 1, the mucous membrane, comprising the epithelium and lamina propria layers, is represented using a layered model. While the submucosa could also be included in the model, it is excluded due to the mucous layer having a thickness of around 2 mm [8], meaning that it is outside the sensing range for the designed probe. σ_{epi} and σ_{lp} represent the electrical conductivity of the epithelium and lamina propria layer respectively, while the thickness of the epithelium layer is presented by h . Three electrodes are placed on the material surface. These present

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Fig. 1. Model representing the UADT mucous membrane. Electrodes are placed on the top layer, representing the tripolar configuration.

the tripolar configuration, with injection electrode i and the two measurement electrodes, m and n .

The electrical properties of tissue include electrical conductivity (σ), which is the material's ability to conduct electric current, and relative permittivity (ϵ_r), which measures its capacity to store electrical energy relative to a vacuum. These properties can be determined using BIS measurements through the following equations.

$$\sigma = \frac{k}{2\pi} \frac{Re_{mn}}{Re_{mn}^2 + Im_{mn}^2} \quad (1)$$

$$\epsilon_r = \frac{k}{4\pi^2 f \epsilon_0} \frac{Im_{mn}}{Re_{mn}^2 + Im_{mn}^2} \quad (2)$$

Where f is the frequency, ϵ_0 is the vacuum permittivity, k is a constant based on the distances between electrodes and the used configuration, and Re_{mn} and Im_{mn} represent the real and imaginary part of impedance, derived from the measured impedance between electrodes m and n .

For the tripolar configuration, k is calculated as:

$$k = \frac{1}{d_m} - \frac{1}{d_n} \quad (3)$$

Where d_m and d_n are the distances between injection electrode i and measurement electrode m and n respectively [7], as depicted in Fig. 1.

When current is injected into a layered material, it partially reflects at the boundary between them. If some of this current reaches a measurement electrode, the conductivity calculated from Eq. 1 will incorporate information from both layers. The estimated conductivity from this calculation is referred to as the apparent conductivity (σ_a). For a layered material, it can be theoretically defined as:

$$\frac{1}{\sigma_a} = \frac{1}{\sigma_{epi}} + \frac{2}{\sigma_{epi}} \frac{dm \cdot dn}{|dm - dn|} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{r^n}{\sqrt{d_m^2 + (2nh)^2}} - \frac{r^n}{\sqrt{d_n^2 + (2nh)^2}} \right) \quad (4)$$

Where the degree of current reflection depends on the reflection coefficient ($r = \frac{\sigma_{epi} - \sigma_{lp}}{\sigma_{epi} + \sigma_{lp}}$), which arises from the conductivity contrast between the two layers [9].

Fig. 2. Left: shows the ellipse shaped probe with the red circle representing the search space. Right: Shows the simplified search space. Each position is translated into a position on the ellipse probe during optimization.

A. Design constraints

When current is injected in a tripolar configuration, it spreads radially in multiple directions, with higher current density near the surface of the material. A measurement electrode placed close to the injection electrode captures primarily superficial current, while an electrode placed at a greater distance senses current that has penetrated deeper into the material [9]. Therefore, having a wide range of distances allows for measurements which include information about a wider range of depths, giving more valuable information which can be used to estimate σ_{epi} , σ_{lp} and h .

The probe is designed to pass through a laryngoscope's working channel, restricting its diameter to 2 mm. It must accommodate four 0.3 mm electrodes while keeping the center available for another application. To ensure sufficient surrounding material, while leaving the center open, the electrodes are positioned 0.65 mm from the probe's center. To maximize electrode spacing within the probe's limited radius, the tip is cut at a 45° angle. This modification increases the surface area, allowing for greater electrode separation. As a result, the search space is defined as a circle with a 0.65 mm radius, where the electrode placement is determined by the angle, as illustrated in Fig. 2.

B. Electrode position optimization

During optimization, the electrodes are simplified to a single point representing their center. Designs where two electrode centers are placed at an angle of less than 45° from each other are excluded to ensure the electrodes do not touch.

The tripolar configuration is chosen for this design because it enables a greater number of measurements compared to the tetrapolar configuration when using four electrodes. The number of possible tetrapolar measurement configurations is given by $\frac{n(n-1)}{2} \cdot \frac{(n-3)(n-2)}{2}$, whereas for the tripolar configuration, it is $n \cdot \frac{(n-2)(n-1)}{2}$ where n represents the number of electrodes placed on the probe. For four electrodes, this results in 12 possible tripolar measurements, whereas the tetrapolar configuration only allows for 6.

For this configuration, the relationship between electrode placement and measurement depth depend on two key factors: (1) The shortest distance between i and one of the measurement electrodes, defined as $\min(d_m, d_n)$ and (2)

the distance between the two measurement electrodes, given by $|d_m - d_n|$. Among these, (1) has a greater influence on the measurement depth than (2) [9]. Based on this theory, optimizing inter-electrode distances enables a broader range of measurement depths. The six inter-electrode distances are represented by the list d . The objective is to maximize the range R , defined as $R = \max(d) - \min(d)$, ensuring some electrodes are positioned far apart while others are placed closer together. The remaining instances in d should be evenly distributed between $\min(d)$ and $\max(d)$. To enforce this distribution, a penalty term P is introduced, defined as:

$$P = \sum_{i=1}^m (d_i - d_{i-1}) - \Delta d_o \quad (5)$$

Where the optimal difference in distance, Δd_o is calculated as $\Delta d_o = R/(m-1)$, with m representing the number of distances between electrodes, calculated $m = \frac{n(n-1)}{2}$.

Based on the included parameters, the final optimization is as follows:

$$\text{Maximize}(R - wP) \quad (6)$$

Where w is a weight for the penalty and set to 1 for this calculation.

C. Electrode shape compensation

While d_m and d_n is defined as the distance between electrode centers, the electrodes have a surface area of ~ 0.1 mm². Therefore, the exact distance between measurement points is unknown [7]. In cases where the electrode surface is round, the same correction value can be used for both d_m and d_n . However, since the electrodes are ellipse shaped for this application, distances between electrode centers and boarders depend on the specific electrodes used. Therefore, two correction values, C_m and C_n are used in eq. 3 as follows:

$$k = \left| \frac{1}{d_m - C_m} - \frac{1}{d_n - C_n} \right| \quad (7)$$

For each configuration, the apparent conductivity σ_a and apparent relative permittivity ϵ_{ra} are calculated using eq. 1 and 2 respectively. The two correction values are optimized by minimizing the error between the actual and apparent electrical properties. The error is defined as:

$$\text{Error} = \sum \frac{|\epsilon_r - \epsilon_{ra}|}{\epsilon_r} + \sum \frac{|\sigma - \sigma_a|}{\sigma} \quad (8)$$

Although the correction values are optimized for a specific material with a set of electrical properties, these same values can be applied to materials with different electrical properties, resulting in more accurate measurements overall.

III. EXPERIMENTS

To evaluate the described methods, three experiments were conducted. Experiment 1 aimed to validate the use of correction values across different materials. Experiments 2 and 3 were designed to assess the performance of the optimized probe for measurements on a layered material. All experiments were based on simulation using COMSOL

Fig. 3. COMSOL model used for simulation.

Multiphysics 6.2. The model involved four cylinder shaped electrodes placed at an angle of 45° on a cube with side-length of 20 mm and a ground electrode was placed on an adjacent side, as depicted in Fig. 3. The setup from the figure was the one used for Experiment 2 and 3, while Experiment 1 was done on a single material cube, replacing the two layers with one.

For all experiments, ϵ_r of the different layers of tissue was set to 20 and six frequencies were used: 50 kHz; 100 kHz; 200 kHz; 400 kHz; 800 kHz and 1.6 MHz. In Experiment 1, 5 conductivities ranging from 0.2 S/m to 1.0 S/m, with a step size of 0.2 S/m were tested, as this range falls within the typical values for human tissues [10]. The correction values for the electrode shape compensation were optimized based on measurements where σ was set to 0.2 S/m and later validated by applying them to the different conductivity settings.

For experiment 2 and 3, the two layers of the cube were made to resemble the epithelium and lamina propria layer. Since the conductivity of each individual layer was not found in the literature, these were estimated using the normal overall conductivity of the mucosa in this area, setting the conductivity of epithelium to 0.4 S/m and the lamina propria layer to 0.7 S/m [11] [12]. In Experiment 2, we compared the optimized probe with two other symmetric probes. The thickness of the epithelium layer (h) was set to 0.35 mm, which corresponds to its normal thickness in the mouth [13]. In Experiment 3, 5 values of h were tested in order to evaluate the performance of the optimized probe on the layered interface measurement. With h normally ranging between 0.3 mm and 0.46 mm [13], a range of 0.3 mm to 0.5 mm were tested, with a step size of 0.05 mm.

IV. RESULTS

Using the optimization method, angles of 90°, 270°, 201° and 315° were found for the four electrodes. The designed probe was compared with two other probes: The rectangle probe and the diamond probe, as seen in Fig. 4. These probe

Fig. 4. Picture of the three evaluated probes. The numbers represent electrode number and the red circle shows the search space.

TABLE I

ACCURACY OF THE DERIVED σ_a FOR EACH CONFIGURATION WITH (W/) AND WITHOUT (W/O) CORRECTION VALUES

	Config.	Accuracy w/o correction[%]	Accuracy w/ correction[%]	Improvement [%]
Diamond	I_1V_{23}	99.54	99.99	0.45
	I_3V_{14}	80.07	100	19.93
	Average	89.805	100	10.19
Square	I_1V_{23}	95.96	100	4.00
	I_1V_{24}	99.04	100	0.96
	I_1V_{34}	93.24	100	6.76
	Average	96.08	100	3.92
Optimized	I_1V_{23}	95.45	100	4.55
	I_1V_{24}	92.25	100	7.75
	I_1V_{34}	85.99	100	14.01
	I_2V_{13}	98.69	100	1.31
	I_2V_{14}	97.51	100	2.49
	I_2V_{34}	94.27	100	5.73
	I_3V_{12}	99.88	100	0.12
	I_3V_{14}	97.55	99.99	2.44
	I_3V_{24}	98.71	100	1.29
	I_4V_{12}	97.81	100	2.19
	I_4V_{13}	93.45	100	6.55
	I_4V_{23}	95.52	100	4.48
	Average	95.59	100	4.41

designs were based on symmetric designs, commonly used for BIS in the literature.

Since each probe has 4 electrodes, 12 different combinations can be generated. The configurations are denoted as I_iV_{mn} where i is the injection electrode while m and n are the measurement electrodes. It can be noticed that, for the diamond probe and the rectangle probe some of the configurations will retrieve identical measurements, due to equal distances such as the I_1V_{23} and I_1V_{24} configurations for the diamond probe. When excluding these measurements, the diamond probe only has two useful configurations, while the rectangle probe has three.

A. Experiment 1

The σ_a of each configuration was found by using eq. 1 for each frequency in the sweep, and calculating the mean of this value. While different conductivities were tested, the accuracy of σ_a in determining σ was the same. Therefore, one accuracy for each configuration is presented in Table I, both with and without using the correction values. The final column highlights the percentage of improvement achieved by using the correction values. From this, it was evident that the accuracy increased with 0.12% to 19.93%, with a higher

Fig. 5. The apparent conductivity of each probe with $h = 0.35$ mm. Simulated results are compared to theoretical ones both with (w/) and without (w/o) the use of correction values.

TABLE II

MSE OF EACH PROBE WITH AND WITHOUT USING CORRECTION VALUES

Probe	MSE w/o correction	MSE w/ correction
Rectangle	0.00034	0.00011
Diamond	0.00117	0.00119
Optimized	0.001	0.00013

improvement indicating a greater effect of using the electrode compensation method for a single material.

B. Experiment 2

In Experiment 2, the probes were evaluated based on their capability of deriving information from the two layers in the scenario where $h = 0.35$ mm. To estimate the accuracy of measurements on a layered material, the derived σ_a was compared to the theoretical value, found by using eq. 4. To evaluate the use of the electrode shape compensation method for a layered material, this comparison was done both with and without using the correction values. These were compared for each probe in Fig. 5 while the Mean-squared-error (MSE) is presented in Table II. Measurements which were approaching that of σ_{lp} indicated that the configuration was capturing currents which has passed through this layer, while lower values which approximates σ_{epi} indicate a configuration was mainly capturing information of the shallow layer. This means that a wide range of σ_a measurements included information from current penetration at different depths.

C. Experiment 3

Using the optimized probe design with correction values applied, the configurations were sorted based on their effective measurement depths, from most superficial to deepest. The correlation between each configuration and the theoretical as well as simulated σ_a can be viewed for different values of h as seen in Fig. 6. To ensure the probe's effectiveness in extracting the desired information, a broad range of σ_a estimations was needed for all cases within the typical range of epithelium thickness (h).

Fig. 6. Apparent conductivity for the optimized probes configurations, ordered by their sensitivity to deeper structures from lowest to highest. This was found for different values of h .

V. DISCUSSION

Optimizing electrode placement based on inter-electrode distances shows promising results for measuring layered materials such as the UADT.

The results from Experiment 1 demonstrate high accuracy in determining the conductivity across all configurations, ranging from 80.1% to 99.9%. Applying correction values further enhances accuracy for every configuration, leading to near 100%. The most significant improvement is observed in configuration $I_3 V_{14}$ for the diamond probe, where accuracy increases by 19.9%. A similar trend is observed in Experiment 2, where the MSE improves for both the rectangular and optimized probes when correction values are applied, though a slight decrease in accuracy is noted for the diamond probe. These results verify the feasibility of this method in improving measurement accuracy for different configurations in both single and layered materials.

Additionally, in Experiment 2, the optimized probe achieves a wide range of σ_a measurements, approximating both σ_{epi} and σ_{lp} with a wide range of measurements in between. This suggests that different configurations capture varying amounts of current passing through the deeper layer, effectively providing measurements with distinct sensitivity distributions. For the symmetric probe designs, the range of σ_a is 0.54 S/m to 0.6 S/m and 0.57 S/m to 0.6 S/m for the diamond probe and rectangle probe respectively, with this small range indicating that the configurations within each probe have similar depth sensitivity. The results from Experiment 3 verify that the probe is capable of retrieving useful information in the entire range of h , due to the measurements maintaining a high difference in σ_a across different values of h . Utilizing the optimization method for probe design and measuring a layered material can facilitate in the development of a method to determine the conductivity of the two layers and the thickness of the top layer, by deriving more information, which can be done in the future work.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study presents an optimized 2 mm BIS sensing probe designed for use with a laryngoscope. Four electrode positions were optimized based on inter-electrode distances, resulting in different sensitivity distributions for each available configuration. Compared to traditional symmetric designs, this probe extracts more information with fewer electrodes when analyzing layered materials. In total, 12 unique measurements are available from this probe, while the tested symmetrical designs achieved two to three unique measurements with these having similar sensitivity distributions. By leveraging a wider depth sensitivity range, the probe enables identification of electrical properties and layer thickness, aiding in tissue differentiation and enhancing early detection of UADT cancer.

REFERENCES

- [1] D. Swaminathan, N. A. George, S. Thomas, and E. M. Iype, "Factors associated with delay in diagnosis of oral cancers," *Cancer Treatment and Research Communications*, vol. 40, p. 100831, 2024.
- [2] J. Bagan, G. Sarrion, and Y. Jimenez, "Oral cancer: clinical features," *Oral oncology*, vol. 46, no. 6, pp. 414–417, 2010.
- [3] M. Brizuela and R. Winters, "Histology, oral mucosa," 2021.
- [4] V. Gupta, U. Agrawal, and P. Goel, "Bioimpedance: A tool for screening oral cancer—a systematic review," *Contemporary Clinical Dentistry*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 91–97, 2023.
- [5] A. A. Pathiraja, R. A. Weerakkody, A. C. von Roon, P. Ziprin, and R. Bayford, "The clinical application of electrical impedance technology in the detection of malignant neoplasms: a systematic review," *Journal of Translational Medicine*, vol. 18, pp. 1–11, 2020.
- [6] Z. Cheng and T. R. Savarimuthu, "Monopolar, bipolar, tripolar, and tetrapolar configurations in robot assisted electrical impedance sensing," *Biomedical Physics & Engineering Express*, vol. 8, no. 5, p. 055014, 2022.
- [7] Z. Cheng, D. Dall'Alba, K. L. Schwaner, P. Fiorini, and T. R. Savarimuthu, "Robot assisted electrical impedance scanning for tissue bioimpedance spectroscopy measurement," *Measurement*, vol. 195, p. 111112, 2022.
- [8] P. H. Montero and S. G. Patel, "Cancer of the oral cavity," *Surgical Oncology Clinics*, vol. 24, no. 3, pp. 491–508, 2015.
- [9] Z. Cheng and T. R. Savarimuthu, "A novel robot-assisted electrical impedance scanning system for subsurface object detection," *Measurement Science and Technology*, vol. 32, no. 8, p. 085902, 2021.
- [10] H. McCann, G. Pisano, and L. Beltrachini, "Variation in reported human head tissue electrical conductivity values," *Brain topography*, vol. 32, pp. 825–858, 2019.
- [11] S. Huang, W. Cai, S. Han, Y. Lin, Y. Wang, F. Chen, G. Shao, Y. Liu, X. Yu, Z. Cai *et al.*, "Differences in the dielectric properties of various benign and malignant thyroid nodules," *Medical Physics*, vol. 48, no. 2, pp. 760–769, 2021.
- [12] D. C. Walker, "Modelling the electrical properties of cervical epithelium." Ph.D. dissertation, University of Sheffield, 2001.
- [13] K.-H. Cho, S.-K. Yu, M.-H. Lee, D.-S. Lee, and H.-J. Kim, "Histological assessment of the palatal mucosa and greater palatine artery with reference to subepithelial connective tissue grafting," *Anatomy & cell biology*, vol. 46, no. 3, pp. 171–176, 2013.